

How crawler extracts data

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General explanation

Overview

This document contains a general description of the crawler developed to extract information automatically from online platforms (Citizen science platforms and others). The steps and substeps that the crawler follows are (Figure 1):

- **Data origin: platforms** - The list of websites with CS projects information (<https://zenodo.org/record/7310295#.Y3dn7naZOUk>) where to extract project information.
- **Platform projects Url extraction**- For each platform, there is a page with a list of projects and each one contains a link to the information.
 - **Platform data cleaning** - once the link information is extracted, as the crawler doesn't distinguish if the urls extracted are correct, there is to remove all the links that are not necessary.
- **Projects data extraction** - For each project link extracted before, there is to extract the project information. As it is required in the CS Track project proposal, the data should be categorized into meaningful categories. The categories defined to classify the information extracted, are called descriptors and are listed in the Descriptor document (<https://zenodo.org/record/7310445#.Y3doG3aZOUk>).
 - **Projects data cleaning** - once the project description and information is extracted, there is to remove all the data that is not relevant to the project or is not related to it.

Figure 1 - Steps followed by crawler

The **technology** used to develop the crawler is python with b4soup and selenium libraries. Data and technical information are stored in mongodb database.

The database structure is based on the steps and substeps that the crawler follows and there are created different collections (Figure 2):

- **platforms_pla_list**, platforms technical information
- **projects_pla_list**, first collection where platforms projects link is stored
- **CSTrack_platforms_projects**, final collection after cleaning data
- **projects_pro_list**, first collection where project information is stored
- **CSTrack_projects_descriptors**, final collection after data cleaning

In order to execute different actions and support this actions that crawler does, different collections have been created (for more information <https://zenodo.org/record/7333866#.Y3doanaZOUk>):

- **CSTrack_check_data_cleaning**, to store information that is used during the cleaning process to know if the extraction has worked correctly.
- **CSTrack_logerror**, if any of the checks were not correct, then an error message is stored.
- **CSTrack_config**, in order to classify descriptors, some texts are stored in the collection.

Figure 2 - Database structure and data flow

MongoDB connection

There is a function that contains connection information to the database. It build and return a connection based on:

- database user account
- database user password
- database host
- database port
- connection string with mongodb information

Collections	N/A
Python libraries	N/A
Python files	CSTrack_Mongo_conn.py
Crawler functions	connection

Table 1 - Information related to MongoDB connection function

Data origin: Platforms

The list of citizen science platforms and is listed in the document (<https://zenodo.org/record/7310295#.Y3dn7naZOUk>). Some additional information such as a unique identifier for each platform, the country or the region of a platform.

We checked if the website can be crawled

(<https://github.com/CS-Track-Code/projectdatabase/wiki/Information-about-robots.txt>). The robots.txt file can be used to identify which platforms allow it to extract data automatically using the crawler, (ex. <https://scistarter.org/robots.txt>). We have checked if “User-agent” is “Allow” or “Disallow” and whether the pages used to extract information are defined as “Disallow” or not.

All the technical requirements are stored in a mongodb identified by Id (same as document) and name collection and are necessary to execute all the steps. There is also a defined element which informs how data is stored in the database (*Automatic* or *Manual*) and if the process can be executed for the platform or not (*yes* or *no*) (Figure 3).

```

_id: ObjectId("5ee0933dcde23f497206f5a7")
Id: 13
Name: "Zooniverse"
Url: "https://www.zooniverse.org/projects"
annexed: ""
check: ""
className: "project-card-list"
buttonName: ""
Country: "World wide"
ProjClassName: Array
  0: "project-home-page"
  1: "columns-container"
Load: "yes"
Platform load: "Automatic"
Projects load: "Automatic"
Type: "CS Platforms"
Wp2 Id: 13
Language: "English"

```

Figure 3 - *platforms_pla_list* collection for platform Id = 13

DB Collections	platforms_pla_list
Python libraries	pymongo
Python files	CSTrack_import_platform.py
Crawler functions	get_Cs_Platform

Table 2 - Information related to Platforms information function

Platform projects Url extraction

The process is executed for all the platforms listed in the previous execution. All the platforms contain a web tab with a list of projects and links to the project description. During this step, crawler extracts the Url and title of each project. For some projects, the class

where the text is placed is informed because selenium library requires this information and for other websites, no class is informed and b4soup library extracts all information available. After that, tags “a” and “h1” or “h2” are extracted in order to extract webpage Url and title. The class information is stored in *platforms_pla_list* in *Class_Name* element.

In some cases, there are buttons to navigate through the webpage and read the whole list of projects. The button information is stored in *platforms_pla_list* in *buttonName* element (Table 3). The structure of each page is similar and the process followed is the same.

DB Collections	platforms_pla_list, projects_pla_list, CsTrack_platforms_projects, CSTRack_check_data_cleaning and CSTRack_log
Python libraries	b4soup, selenium and pymongo
Python files	CSTRack_webscraping_retrieve_platforms.py
Crawler functions	retrieve_platforms get_Cs_Platform_Projects get_driver get_elem get_items insert_Platform_Projects_database extract_insert_projects_platforms get_buttons

Table 3 - Information related to Platforms projects Url extraction function

Platforms data cleaning

Data extraction follows data cleaning. The first step is to identify if the number of projects loaded is correct. For this reason, there is a collection called *CSTRack_check_data_cleaning* (Table 4) that contains a document with a list of platforms and the information of the last execution. If this check goes wrong then it inserts a new document in *CSTRack_logerror* with the error information.

Last step is to load information into *CSTRack_paltforms_projects* (Table 4). Some rules are defined in order to not to load documents that contain a certain text in Url element or Name.

DB Collections	platforms_pla_list, projects_pla_list, CsTrack_platforms_projects, CSTRack_check_data_cleaning and CSTRack_log
Python libraries	pymongo
Python files	CSTRack_datacleaning_platforms.py
Crawler functions	Datacleaning_platforms check_num_projects check_data_cleaning

	check_links insert_information
--	-----------------------------------

Table 4 - Information related to Platforms data cleaning function

Projects data extraction

For each project link stored in the database, there is opened and extracted project information. At this point there are different possibilities about how the information is placed in terms of technical requirements:

- **Without class information:** *b4soup* python library is used to read the whole page.
- **With one class informed:** *selenium* python library is used to read the specific class (one class is informed) of the web page.
- **With more than one class informed:** *selenium* python library is used to read the list of classes (more than one class is informed) of the web page.

This information is placed in *platforms_pla_list* collection in *ProjClassName* element.

Once it is known, there is to extract specific tags where information is placed and stored in a list of values:

- tag “a”: contains mail information or Url
- tag “p”: contains text
- tag “li”: contains text in a list of values
- tag “tr”: contains text in a table
- tag “h1”: contains text as a title
- tag “h2”: contains text as a subtitle (in some platforms used as a title)
- tag “h6”: contains text as a small title (in some platforms used as a title)

For each tag, different information is extracted. This information is classified based on the information that contains and the descriptors defined. The list of descriptors (<https://zenodo.org/record/7310445#.Y3doG3aZOUk>) defined for the classification are based on [PPSR_CORE metadata standard](#). The conditions to classify its are:

- If the value contains “@” then the descriptor is “contact info”
- If the value contains “www.” or “http” or not space in the text then it is checked if any of the values defined in *CSTrack_config* collection is in the text extracted:
 - Social media descriptor
 - Resources descriptor
 - Apps descriptor
 - Images descriptor
 - Participants age descriptor
 - Topics descriptor
 - Main program or person in charge descriptor
 - Participants profile descriptor

- Geolocation descriptor
- Web descriptor if is none of the previous descriptors
- If value extracted is none of the previous descriptor then it is checked if is (Figures 4, 5 and 6):
 - Apps descriptor
 - Geolocation descriptor
 - Status descriptor
 - Methodology descriptor
 - Start date descriptor
 - Investment descriptor
 - Topics descriptor
 - Main objectives descriptor
 - Development time descriptor
 - Participants age descriptor
 - Dedication time descriptor
 - Platform update date descriptor
 - Participants profile descriptor
 - Main program or person in charge
 - Tools and materials descriptor
 - Number of members descriptor
 - End date descriptor
 - Web descriptor
 - Description descriptor if is none of the previous descriptors

```

_id: ObjectId("5eaa7c36474c0ad1c81cd37c")
Id: 6
Name: "Social media values"
values: Array
  0: "twitter"
  1: "naver"
  2: "facebook"
  3: "youtube"
  4: "instagram"
  5: "blog."
  6: "PERFILES DEL PROYECTO EN REDES SOCIALES:"
  7: "REDES SOCIALES:"
  8: "PERFILES EN REDES SOCIALES:"
  9: "flickr"

```

Figure 4 - CSTrack_config

```

_id: ObjectId("5eb5406769c62c46187847f1")
Id: 15
Name: "Geographical location"
values: Array
  0: "Geographical"
  1: "Geographic Scope"
  2: "Geographic"
  3: "WHERE"
  4: "Country"
  5: "Ubicación"
  6: "places"
  7: "PROVINCIA:"
  8: "País "
  9: "Project Location"
  10: "Location"

```

Figure 5 - CSTrack_config

```

_id: ObjectId("5ecce1c4c145ed0d20be478b")
Id: 29
Name: "Participants profile"
values: Array
  0: "Wie kan meedoen?"
  1: "Usuarios"
  2: "/people/"
  3: "PÚBLICO AL QUE SE DIRIGE EL PROYECTO:"
  4: "INTEGRANTES DEL PROYECTO:"
  5: "INTEGRANTES:"
  6: "Who can take part?"
  7: "Public : "
  8: "Project Partners"
  9: "Users"

```

Figure 6 - CSTrack_config

After inserting descriptors a dictionary is created with all the lists. Finally, it is checked if there was a connection error during the extraction process or if the title contains a text error and a new document is inserted in *CSTrack_logerror*. If no errors are detected then, the dictionary is inserted in *projects_pla_list* (Table 5).

DB Collections	platforms_pla_list, projects_pla_list, CsTrack_platforms_projects, CSTrack_check_data_cleaning and CSTrack_logerror
Python libraries	b4soup, selenium and pymongo
Python files	CSTrack_webscraping_retrieve_projects.py
Crawler functions	retrieve_projects descriptors_definition execute_process get_driver projects_descriptors get_elem get_items checkDescriptors dictionaryConversion insert_descriptors check_errors language

Table 5 - Information related to projects data extraction function

Projects data cleaning

Last step is to clean the data extracted stored in *projects_pla_list*. First it is checked if the number of projects are correct based on the information stored in *CSTrack_check_data_cleaning*. After that, if there are no errors all the information extracted for each platform (Id) is moved to *STG_projects_pro_list* where all the cleaning process is done.

To clean the data, the information is analyzed and it is defined some common criteria for all the online platforms to remove information that is not correctly classified or is not related to the project. Some of the conditions defined to check data are:

- Remove empty elements, “@”, spaces and “*” in Description list
- Remove all the elements that contains “javascript:” text in Description list

As each platform has specific criteria and issues when data is extracted. There are to define specific conditions to remove data for each platform like:

- Remove certain text in Description and Web list
- Remove elements that contains certain text in Description or Web list
- Remove elements with certain text in title list
- Add new elements if condition is set (For example, for Platform Id = 13 if information contains a text in description, the status is set to “FINISHED”)
- Classify web and description information to other descriptors (For example, for platform Id = 13 or Id = 184 or Id = 65)
- Replace texts from vales of descriptors (For example, Id = 111)
- Split a text and classify it in two different descriptors (For example, Id = 30 Start and End date)

After cleaning the data, the final step is to move all the documents by Id to the final collection *CSTrack_projects_description* (Table 6).

DB Collections	platforms_pla_list, projects_pla_list, CsTrack_platforms_projects, CSTrack_check_data_cleaning, STG_projects_pro_list, CSTrack_projects_description and CSTrack_log
Python libraries	pymongo
Python files	CSTrack_datacleaning_projects.py
Crawler functions	Datacleaning_projects Check_num_projects STG_insert_all Check_descriptors language FIN_insert_all

Table 6 - Information related to projects data cleaning function

Bi-monthly execution

All the processes will be executed two times per month each 15 days. As it is not expected a big amount of new projects, buttons will not be informed so the crawler will not read all the information of the platform, only the first page (if it contains buttons) of each one. We analyzed how platforms organize projects and new ones are informed first in the list. New

information of previous projects loaded will not be loaded during this execution. Special executions are planned to actualize database data for those platforms that need to be updated fully.

Steps followed to execute all the crawler are:

1. Retrieve platforms

- 1.1. Remove all the information loaded in previous execution in projects_pla_list collection
- 1.2. Execute retrieve_platforms function stored in CSTrack_webscraping_retrieve_platforms
- 1.3. Clean data extracted executing data_cleaning_platforms from CSTrack_datacleaning_platforms

2. Retrieve projects

- 2.1. Execute retrieve_projects function stored in CSTrack_webscraping_retrieve_projects
- 2.2. Clean data extracted executing data_cleaning_platforms from CSTrack_datacleaning_projects

Each step inserts a message in *CSTrack_logerror collection* (Table 7) if each one has been executed successfully. Otherwise, insert an error message.

DB Collections	projects_pla_list, projects_pro_list and CSTrack_logerror
Python libraries	pymongo, CSTrack_Mongo_conn, sys, CSTrack_webscraping_retrieve_platforms, CSTrack_datacleaning_platforms, CSTrack_webscraping_retrieve_projects,
Python files	CSTrack_2times_month_exec.py
Crawler functions	All

Table 7 - Information related to Bi-monthly execution process

Error management

In order to show all the errors or warnings that appear during execution in CSTrack_logerror two (Figure 7 and Figure 8) visualizations are developed in Metabase client tool to explore in a simple way how the execution was.

Figure 7 - List of errors stored in previous executions

Figure 8 - Number of errors raised by date

It has developed a pulse in metabase tool that sends an email once a week with this visualization (Figure 9).

Figure 9 - Number of errors raised by date

Examples

In the following, we provide two examples (1) Zooniverse -Disk detective (2) iNaturalist and (3) Citizen science Germany to describe how crawler works.

Example 1 - Zooniverse

In this example it is shown the process to extract data from the [Disk detective](#) project placed in the Zooniverse platform.

The platform where we extract the list of projects is <https://www.zooniverse.org> and we identified this platform with the *Id*: 13 as it can see in the *platforms_pla_list* collection (see <https://github.com/CS-Track-Code/projectdatabase> for more information). We also identified other relevant information and stored it in this list, like the data status, which is placed in columns R, S, T and U and correspond to the steps explained before.

All the information related to the technical requirements of the platform is stored in *platforms_pla_list* collection (Figure 10). Filtering data by *Id:13* shows Zooniverse platform information:

```
_id: ObjectId("5ee0933dcde23f497206f5a7")
Id: 13
Name: "Zooniverse"
Url: "https://www.zooniverse.org/projects"
annexed: ""
check: ""
className: "project-card-list"
buttonName: ""
Country: "World wide"
ProjClassName: Array
  0: "project-home-page"
  1: "columns-container"
Load: "yes"
Platform load: "Automatic"
Projects load: "Automatic"
Type: "CS Platforms"
Wp2 Id: 13
Language: "English"
```

Figure 10 - *platforms_pla_list* collection

First step is to extract platform projects Url from the “projects” web tab where the list of projects is. We will extract the Url and title of project information that is placed in class “*project-card-list*”. (see Figure 11).

Figure 11 - Zooniverse platform and html code to identify the class where information is placed.

For each element in the class, the crawler extracts the information and stores it in collection *projects_pla_list* with the platform country ISO code, the insert date and the Ids (see Figure 12 and 13).

Figure 12 - Zooniverse platform and html code to identify the tag with all the information

```

_id: ObjectId("5ee09cf5612a6cd6439d148c")
Id: 13
Url: "https://www.zooniverse.org/projects/ssilverberg/disk-detective"
Name: "DISK DETECTIVE"
Country: "World"
load_date: "2020-06-10"
Wp2 Id: 13

```

Figure 13 - Document with “Disk detective” information stored in *projects_pla_list* collection

In Zoonivers, there is a list of buttons that redirects to different pages where projects are placed. The crawler find buttons by tag “button” using *find_elements_by_tag_name("button")* function. The structure of each page is the same as the first one so the crawler extracts the elements placed in the same class.

Figure 14 - Zooniverse platform and the list of buttons

Once all the list of buttons has been tracked, the next step is to clean all the Urls that are not usable links. If no data has to be removed, then all the documents with *Id:13* are stored in *CSTrack_platforms_projects* (Figure 15).

```

_id: ObjectId("5ee0a178cea0b9650862c101")
Id: 13
Url: "https://www.zooniverse.org/projects/ssilverberg/disk-detective"
Name: "DISK DETECTIVE"
Country: "World"
load_date: "2020-06-10"
Wp2 Id: 13

```

Figure 15 - Document with “Disk detective” information stored in *CSTrack_platforms_projects* collection

Next step is to extract data from project pages. Once we have the link to each platform project, we can open each web page one by one and read the information. At this point there are different possibilities about how the information is placed in terms of technical requirements.

Once again, we have to store technical information regarding the page structure in *platforms_pla_list* collection (Figure 16). In this case, the element ProjClassName stores a list of classes where data is placed.

```
_id: ObjectId("5ee0933dcde23f497206f5a7")
Id: 13
Name: "Zooniverse"
Url: "https://www.zooniverse.org/projects"
annexed: ""
check: ""
className: "project-card-list"
buttonName: ""
Country: "World wide"
ProjClassName: Array
  0: "project-home-page"
  1: "columns-container"
Load: "yes"
Platform load: "Automatic"
Projects load: "Automatic"
Type: "CS Platforms"
Wp2 Id: 13
Language: "English"
```

Figure 16 - *platforms_pla_list* collection

In this zooniverse case, there are different tabs for each project (Figure 17):

- Main page
- About tab
 - Research tab
 - The team tab
 - Education tab
 - Results tab
 - FAQ tab

Figure 17 - Disk detective page in zooniverse platform

For the *Main page* tab, the information is placed in class “*project-home-page*” and for other pages, the information is placed in class “*columns-container*”.

There are different elements to extract and those have different tags. For each one identified, we use selenium function “*find_elements_by_tag_name*” and store it in a list (Figures 18, 19 and 20):

- *p* tag: usually contains text.

Figure 18 - Disk detective page in zooniverse platform. Tag *p* with text description.

Figure 19 - Disk detective Research tab in zooniverse platform. Tag *p* with text description.

- *a* tag: contains links, usually with <http:> text in the beginning.

Figure 20 - Disk detective The team tab in zooniverse platform. Tag *a* with text description.

Once all the text of each element is extracted, this information is classified based on the text that contains and the list of descriptors defined (see section [Projects data extraction](#) section). For example, for **social media descriptor**, we identified some words or expressions that text extracted could contain. In collection *CSTrack_config* there are different lists with cases for each descriptor (Figures 21 and 22):

```

    _id: ObjectId("5eaa7c36474c0ad1c81cd37c")
    Id: 6
    Name: "Social media values"
    values: Array
      0: "twitter"
      1: "naver"
      2: "facebook"
      3: "youtube"
      4: "instagram"
      5: "blog."
      6: "://blog."
      7: "PERFILES DEL PROYECTO EN REDES SOCIALES:"

```

Figure 21 - CSTrack_config collection with a document for social media descriptor

```

    _id: ObjectId("5f59f640cb5782a2b78a8cd5")
    TITLE: "DISK DETECTIVE"
    WEB: Array
    SOCIAL MEDIA: Array
      0: "https://blog.diskdetective.org/"
      1: "https://twitter.com/diskdetective"
      2: "https://facebook.com/DiskDetect"
      3: "https://blog.galaxyzoo.org/2008/01/10/in-the-eye-of-the-beholder/"
      4: "https://blog.diskdetective.org/2014/02/01/spectral-energy-distribution..."
      5: "https://blog.diskdetective.org/2015/02/15/examples-of-seds/"
      6: "https://blog.diskdetective.org/2014/02/02/the-power-and-danger-of-simb..."
      7: "https://blog.diskdetective.org/2014/02/20/thats-no-moon/"
      8: "https://blog.diskdetective.org/2014/02/04/why-do-the-stars-seem-to-gro..."

```

Figure 22 - *projects_pro_list* collection with the "Disk Detective" project document and social media information classified in Social media descriptor.

In this zooniverse case, there are specific pages for each project that contains information that has to be stored in a specific descriptor. Once the information is read for each tag in class defined, then all the information is filtered by Url and stored in following descriptors (Figure 23):

- Research tab: stored in Description descriptor.
- The team tab: stored in participants profile descriptor.
- Education tab: stored in resources descriptor.
- Results tab: stored in results descriptor.
- FAQ tab: stored in methodology descriptor.

```

    _id: ObjectId("5f59f640cb5782a2b78a8cd5")
    TITLE: "DISK DETECTIVE"
    WEB: Array
    SOCIAL MEDIA: Array
    MAIL: Array
    DESCRIPTION: Array
      Plat Id: "13"
      Plat country: "World"
      Insert date: "2020-09-10"
    IMAGES: Array
    GEOGRAPHICAL LOCATION: Array
    METHODOLOGY: Array
      Url platform: "https://www.zooniverse.org/projects/ssilverberg/disk-detective"
    PARTICIPANTS PROFILE: Array
    RESULTS: Array

```

Figure 23 - "Disk detective" document stored in *projects_pro_list* collection which contains the list of descriptors and information classified

Finally, to inform the title, it is extracted information from tags *h1*, *h2* and *h3*. In this case, as the title is informed out of the classes defined to recover the data and to not to extract

unnecessary information, the title is recovered from the document stored in *CSTrack_platforms_projects* (Figure 24).

Once all the information is extracted and classified, the data cleaning process removes all the information that is not necessary in order to get all the relevant one. For example, from the Main page, crawler extracts text like “blog”, “Learn more” or “Get started”.

```
_id: ObjectId("5f59f640cb5782a2b78a8cd5")
TITLE: "DISK DETECTIVE"
> WEB: Array
> SOCIAL MEDIA: Array
> MAIL: Array
< DESCRIPTION: Array
  0: "2 people are talking about Disk Detective right now."
  1: "Blog"
  2: "NASA Citizen Science"
  3: "diskdetective"
  4: "DiskDetect"
  5: "Learn more"
  6: "Get started"
  7: "Join in"
```

Figure 24 - “Disk detective” document stored in *projects_pro_list* collection. Example of description descriptors to remove.

This process is done in *STG_projects_pro_list* and after “cleaning” it, if this project has not been stored in *CSTrack_projects_descriptors* collection yet, the process inserts the whole document there (Figure 25). If it exists in the collection, then those descriptors that contain additional information are updated.

```
_id: ObjectId("5f59f640cb5782a2b78a8cd5")
TITLE: "DISK DETECTIVE"
> WEB: Array
> SOCIAL MEDIA: Array
> MAIL: Array
> DESCRIPTION: Array
  Plat Id: "13"
  Plat country: "World"
  Insert date: "2020-09-10"
> IMAGES: Array
> GEOGRAPHICAL LOCATION: Array
> METHODOLOGY: Array
  Url platform: "https://www.zooniverse.org/projects/ssilverberg/disk-detective"
> PARTICIPANTS PROFILE: Array
> RESULTS: Array
```

Figure 25 - “Disk detective” document stored in *CSTrack_projects_descriptors* collection which contains the list of descriptors and information classified.

Example 2 - iNaturalist

In this example process to extract data from the [Lukel a Klengar: Ngardok Nature Reserve. Melekeok](#) and ["Milkweed Madness" Monarch Waystation](#) project from iNaturalist platform are described.

The platform where we extract the list of projects is <https://www.inaturalist.org/> and we identified this platform with the *Id: 111* as it can see in the *platforms_pla_list* collection (see <https://github.com/CS-Track-Code/projectdatabase> for more information).

All the information related to platform technical requirements is stored in *platforms_pla_list* collection (Figure 26). Filtering data by *Id: 111* shows iNaturalist platform information:

```

_id: ObjectId("5e8ae2820860f8e2f623ee20")
Id: 111
Name: "inaturalista network"
Url: "https://www.inaturalist.org/projects/browse"
annexed: "https://www.inaturalist.org"
check: "/projects/"
className: ""
buttonName: "//a[@class='next_page']"
Country: "World wide"
> ProjClassName: Array
Load: "yes"
Platform load: "Automatic"
Projects load: "Automatic"
Type: "CS Platforms"
Wp2 Id: 5
Language: "Multiple"

```

Figure 26 - *platforms_pla_list* collection

First step is to extract platform projects Url from the “projects” web tab where the list of projects is. In this case, we use b4soup python library. In *platforms_pla_list* collection we don’t inform the class because this library doesn’t use this information to extract data. Instead, we check if a specific value is in data extracted because the project’s url contains the text “/projects/” and the crawler only gets it. Additionally, because the information extracted from “a” tag (where the Url is placed) is not complete, it has to add an annexed text “<http://www.inaturalist.org/projects/browse>” (Figures 27 and 28). Both information (check and annexed) are informed in *platforms_pla_list* collection.

Figure 27 - “Lukel a Klengar: Ngardok Nature Reserve, Melekeok” link placed in iNaturalist platform

Figure 28 - “Lukel a Klengar: Ngardok Nature Reserve, Melekeok” project Url

There is a list of buttons that redirects to different project pages. The structure of each page is the same as the first one so the crawler extracts the elements placed in the same class (Figure 29).

Figure 29- iNaturalist platform and the list of buttons

For each element, the crawler extracts the information and stores it in collection *projects_pla_list* with the platform country ISO code, the insert date and the Ids (Figure 30).

```

_id: ObjectId("5eda2ee2052ac24d176d5c91")
Id: 111
Url: "https://www.inaturalist.org/projects/lukel-a-klengar-ngardok-nature-re..."
Name: ""Lukel a Klengar: Ngardok Nature Reserve, Melekeok""
Country: "World"
load_date: "2020-06-05"
Wp2 Id: 5

```

Figure 30 - "Lukel a Klengar: Ngardok Nature Reserve, Melekeok" document in *projects_pla_list* collection

Once all the list of buttons has been tracked, the next step is to clean all the Urls that are not usable links. Because crawler doesn't extract information from a concrete class, the data that contains the text '<https://www.inaturalist.org/projects/new>' and '<https://www.inaturalist.org/projects/browse?page=>' has to be removed. After this process, then all the documents with *Id: 111* are stored in *CSTrack_platforms_projects* (Figure 31).

```

_id: ObjectId("5ee085f0c12df83c607172b2")
Id: 111
Url: "https://www.inaturalist.org/projects/lukel-a-klengar-ngardok-nature-re..."
Name: ""Lukel a Klengar: Ngardok Nature Reserve, Melekeok""
Country: "World"
load_date: "2020-06-10"
Wp2 Id: 5

```

Figure 31 - "Lukel a Klengar: Ngardok Nature Reserve, Melekeok" document in *CSTrack_platforms_projects*.

Second step is to extract data from project pages. Once we have the link to each platform project, we can open it one by one and read the information. In iNaturalist platform, there are two types of structures for the project definition. For each one, the information is placed in different places. In this case, the element *ProjClassName* stores is not informed in *platforms_pla_list* collection (Figures 32 and 33).

"Lukel a Klengar: Ngardok Nature Reserve, Melekeok"

A Ngardok Nature Reserve el ngar er a beluu er a Melekeok er a Belau a ngar er ngii a betok el bedengel a charm me a dellomel el ngar er a chesel. Tial Reserve a ngar er ngii a kakerous el basio er a chesel el blii e lukel a kakerous el bedengel a charm me a dellomel Aika el basio a uldimukl er ngii a omoachel, delomeklochel, oreomel, me a ked. A Ngardok Lake me ng dirrek el ngar er a chesel tial Reserve. A belkul a Ngardok a madedok el ngii a kot el klou el omoachel er a chesel a Micronesia.

Tial omoachel me a delmeklochel el iliuekl er ngii a kot el meklou a ultutelel el blii a:

Charm el Suebek:

Ng betok el bedengel a charm el suebek el ikel el di de betik er a Belau el diak er a ngodech el beluu er a Beluulechad el ua ia debar, beloachel, me a melimdelebeteb. Ng dirrek el sebeched el mes a

Project Requirements

Observations in this project must meet the following criteria:

Taxa	All taxa
Location	Ngardok Nature Reserve
Users	any
Projects	any
Quality Grade	any
Media Type	any
Date	any
Establishment	any

Figure 32 - "Lukel a Klengar: Ngardok Nature Reserve, Melekeok" project information structure

"Milkweed Madness" Monarch Waystation

Stats

<p>Totals</p> <p>7 Observations »</p> <p>? Species »</p> <p>1 People »</p>	<p>Most Observations</p> <p> Unknown</p>		
---	--	--	---

» **Members**

 [View All Members »](#)

» **Export Observations**

[Atom / CSV](#)

About

To document the habitat and ecosystem of our Monarch Waystation, "Milkweed Madness."

 nicolelucier created this project on September 03, 2017

Figure 33 - "Milkweed Madness" Monarch Waystation project information structure

There are different elements to extract and those have different tags. For each one identified, we use b4soup function "find_all()" and store it in a list (Figures 34, 35, 36, 37 and 38):

- p tag: usually contains text (Figures 34 and 35).

Figure 34 - "Lukel a Klengar: Ngardok Nature Reserve, Melekeok" project information structure. "p" tag.

Figure 35 - "Milkweed Madness" Monarch Waystation project information structure. "p" tag.

- tr tag: table with text classified (Figure 36).

Figure 36 - "Lukel a Klengar: Ngardok Nature Reserve, Melekeok" project information structure. "tr" tag.

- a tag: contains links, usually with http: text in the beginning (Figures 37 and 38).

Figure 37 - “Lukel a Klengar: Ngardok Nature Reserve, Melekeok” project information structure. “tr” tag.

Figure 38 - “Milkweed Madness” Monarch Waystation project information structure. “a” tag.

Once all the text elements are extracted, they are classified based on the text that it contains. For example, for **each element in the table** (tr tag), we identified some words or expressions that the extracted text may contain. In collection *CSTrack_config* there are different lists with cases for each descriptor (Figure 39):

Taxa	All taxa	<code>_id: ObjectId("5eb5406769c62c46187847f1")</code>	<code>_id: ObjectId("5ecce1c4c145ed0d20be478b")</code>
Location	Ngardok Nature Reserve	Id: 15 Name: "Geographical location"	Id: 29 Name: "Participants profile"
Users	any	<code> values: Array 0: "Geographical" 1: "Geographic Scope" 2: "Geographic" 3: "WHERE" 4: "Country" 5: "Ubicación" 6: "places" 7: "PROVINCIA:" 8: "País " 9: "Project Location" </code>	<code> values: Array 0: "Wie kan meedoen?" 1: "Usuarios" 2: "/people/" 3: "PÚBLICO AL QUE SE DIRIGE EL PROYECTO:" 4: "INTEGRANTES DEL PROYECTO:" 5: "INTEGRANTES:" 6: "Who can take part?" 7: "Public : " 8: "Project Partners" 9: "Users" </code>
Projects	any		
Quality Grade	any		
Media Type	any		
Date	any		
Establishment	any		

Figure 39 - “Lukel a Klengar: Ngardok Nature Reserve, Melekeok” project, *CSTrack_config* collection with a document for geographical location and participants profile descriptors

Finally, to inform the title, it is extracted information from tags *h1*, *h2* and *h3*. For those tags the title extracted is “*Estadísticas del evento*” or “*Estadísticas*”. The text extracted is not the real title of the projects, that is why the title is recovered from the document stored in *CSTrack_platforms_projects*.

When all the information is extracted and classified, the data cleaning process removes all the information that is not necessary in order to get all the relevant one. For example, crawler extracts text like “*Acerca de*”, “*Ayuda*” or “*Foro*” (Figure 40 and 41).

```

_id: ObjectId("5ef5e74150851032680dd179")
TITLE: ""Lukel a Klengar: Ngardok Nature Reserve, Melekeok""
DESCRIPTION: Array
  0: "Proyectos : cualquiera"
  1: "Grado de calidad : cualquiera"
  2: "Clasificación : cualquiera"
  3: "A Ngardok Nature Reserve el ngar er a beluu er a Melekeok er a Belau a..."
  4: "- February 12, 2019"
  5: "kobori"
  6: "bcrainium"
  7: "Acerca de"
  8: "Ayuda"

```

Figure 40 - “Lukel a Klengar: Ngardok Nature Reserve, Melekeok” project

```

_id: ObjectId("5ef5e97350851032680dd17a")
"
TITLE: "Milkweed Madness" Monarch Waystation
"
DESCRIPTION: Array
0: ""
1: "On our front porch, brought in to watch turn. "
2: "On river birch. "
3: "Front foundation garden, on witch hazel shrub. "
4: "Front garden, on the winterberry. "
5: "Front garden. "
6: "Front garden."
7: "To document the habitat and ecosystem of our Monarch Waystation, "Milk..."
"
¿Esto es inapropiado, spam u ofensivo?
8:
Agregar una marca
"
"
9: Acerca de
"
"
10: Ayuda
"

```

Figure 41 - "Milkweed Madness" Monarch Waystation project

This process is done in *STG_projects_pro_list* and after “cleaning” it, if this project has not been stored in *CSTrack_projects_descriptors* collection yet, the process inserts the whole document there (Figures 42 and 43). If it exists in the collection, then those descriptors that contain additional information are updated.

```

_id: ObjectId("5ef5e74150851032680dd179")
TITLE: "Lukel a Klengar: Ngardok Nature Reserve, Melekeok"
DESCRIPTION: Array
0: "Proyectos : cualquiera"
1: "Grado de calidad : cualquiera"
2: "Clasificación : cualquiera"
3: "A Ngardok Nature Reserve el ngar er a beluu er a Melekeok er a Belau a..."
4: "- February 12, 2019"
5: "kobori"
6: "bcrainium"
7: "A Ngardok Nature Reserve el ngar er a beluu er a Melekeok er a Belau a..."
Plat Id: "111"

```

Figure 42 - “Lukel a Klengar: Ngardok Nature Reserve, Melekeok” project

```

_id: ObjectId("5ef5e97350851032680dd17a")
"
TITLE: "Milkweed Madness" Monarch Waystation
"
DESCRIPTION: Array
0: "On our front porch, brought in to watch turn. "
1: "On river birch. "
2: "Front foundation garden, on witch hazel shrub. "
3: "Front garden, on the winterberry. "
4: "Front garden. "
5: "Front garden."
6: "To document the habitat and ecosystem of our Monarch Waystation, "Milk..."
7: "Papilio troilus"
8: "Macremphytus testaceus"
9: "Superfamilia Tenthredinoidea"
10: "Superfamilia"
11: "Tenthredinoidea"

```

Figure 43 - "Milkweed Madness" Monarch Waystation project

Example 3 - Citizen science Germany

In this example the process to extract data from the [Spielerisch Daten erheben](#) project placed in the German Citizen science platform are described

The platform where we extract the list of projects is <http://www.citizen-science-germany.de> and we identified this platform with the *Id*: 32 as it can see in the *platforms_pla_list* collection (see <https://github.com/CS-Track-Code/projectdatabase> for more information).

All the information related to platform technical requirements is stored in *platforms_pla_list* collection (Figure 44). Filtering data by *Id*: 32 shows German Citizen science platform information:

```
_id: ObjectId("5ee0d8d338210d2dacd07e0f")
Id : 32
Name : "Citizen Science Germany "
Url : "http://www.citizen-science-germany.de/citizen_science_germany_projekte.html
annexed : "http://www.citizen-science-germany.de/ "
check : "citizen_science_germany_projekte "
className : " "
buttonName : " "
Country : "DE "
ProjClassName : " "
Load : "yes "
Platform load : "Automatic "
Projects load : "Automatic "
Type : "CS Platforms "
Wp2 Id : 32
Language : "German "
```

Figure 44 - *platforms_pla_list* collection

First step is to extract platform projects Url from the ["projekte" web tab](#) where the list of projects is. In this case, we use *b4soup* python library. In *platforms_pla_list* collection we don't inform the class because this library doesn't use this information to extract data. Instead, we check if a specific value is in data extracted because the project's url contains the text *"citizen_science_germany_projekte"* and the crawler only gets it. Additionally, because the information extracted from *"a"* tag (where the Url is placed) is not complete, it has to add an annexed text *"http://www.citizen-science-germany.de/"* (Figures 45 and 46). Both information (check and annexed) are informed in *platforms_pla_list* collection.

Figure 45 - *Spielerisch Daten erheben* project link placed in Germany citizen science platform

Figure 46 - "Spielerisch Daten erheben" project Url

For each element, the crawler extracts the information and stores it in collection *projects_pla_list* with the platform country ISO code, the insert date and the Ids (Figure 47).

```
_id: ObjectId("5ee0d8ea38210d2dacd07e10")
Id: 32
Url: "http://www.citizen-science-germany.de/citizen_science_germany_projekte..."
Name: "PROJEKTE"
Country: "DEU"
load_date: "2020-06-10"
```

Figure 47 - Spielerisch Daten erheben project stored in *projects_pla_list* collection

In this case, there are no buttons; the next step is to clean all the Urls that are not usable links. Because crawler doesn't extract information from a concrete class, the data that contains the text "http://www.citizen-science-germany.de/citizen_science_germany_projekte.html" has to be removed. After this process, all the documents with *Id:32* are stored in *CSTrack_platforms_projects*. Title is not well informed but it will be fixed during the next step (Figure 48).

```
_id: ObjectId("5ee0d96e0939497230bebe7c")
Id: 32
Url: "http://www.citizen-science-germany.de/citizen_science_germany_projekte..."
Name: "» Zum aktuellen Projekt"
Country: "DEU"
load_date: "2020-06-10"
Wp2 Id: 32
```

Figure 48 - Spielerisch Daten erheben project stored in *CSTrack_platforms_projects*

Second step is to extract data from project pages. Once we have the link to each platform project (Figure 49), we can open it one by one and read the information. In this case, crawler uses *b4soup* python library because the class where the information is placed is not informed.

```
_id: ObjectId("5ee0d8d338210d2dacd07e0f")
Id : 32
Name : "Citizen Science Germany "
Url : "http://www.citizen-science-germany.de/citizen_science_germany_projekte.html"
annexed : "http://www.citizen-science-germany.de/"
check : "citizen_science_germany_projekte "
className : " "
buttonName : " "
Country : "DE "
ProjClassName : " "
Load : "yes "
Platform load : "Automatic "
Projects load : "Automatic "
Type : "CS Platforms "
Wp2 Id : 32
Language : "German "
```

Figure 49 - *platforms_pla_list* collection

There are different elements to extract and those have different tags. For each one identified, we use *b4soup* function "*find_all()*" and store it in a list (Figures 50 and 51):

- p tag: usually contains text.

Figure 50 - “Spielerisch Daten erheben” project

- a tag: contains links, usually with http: text in the beginning.

Figure 51 - “Gemeinsam in einem Boot” project

Once all the text elements are extracted, they are classified based on the text that contains (Figure 52).

```

_id: ObjectId("5f4cb1b60f142d4cc42c6521")
TITLE: "Spielerisch Daten erheben"
> DESCRIPTION: Array
  Plat Id: "32"
  Plat country: "DEU"
  Insert date: "2020-08-31"
> STATUS: Array
  Url platform: "http://www.citizen-science-germany.de/citizen_science_germany_projekte..."

```

Figure 52 - “Spielerisch Daten erheben” document stored in *projects_pro_list* collection which contains the list of descriptors and information classified

Finally, to inform the title, information from tags *h1*, *h2* and *h3* are extracted (Figure 53).

Figure 53 - “Spielerisch Daten erheben” project title, *h1* tag.

When all the information is extracted and classified, the data cleaning process removes all the unnecessary information to keep only the relevant one. For example, crawler extracts text like “HOME”, “citizenscience:germany” or “IMPRESSUM” (Figure 54).

```

_id: ObjectId("5f4cb1b60f142d4cc42c6521")
TITLE: "Spielerisch Daten erheben"
DESCRIPTION: Array
  0: ""
  1: "HOME"
  2: "citizenscience:germany"
  3: "IMPRESSUM"
  4: "DATENSCHUTZ"
  5: "BERICHTE/KOMMENTARE"
  6: "PROJEKTE"
  7: "IDEEN"
  8: "ONLINE-DOSSIER"
  9: "Dahinter verbirgt sich ein mobiles App-Spiel, mit dem Wissenschaftler ..."
  10: "Sea Hero Quest ist jedoch nicht nur einfach ein weiteres App-Spiel von..."
  11: "Interview"
  12: ""
  13: "Herr Dr. Wehmeier, die Telekom unterstützt mit einem App-Spiel die Dem..."
  14: "Da gibt es schon ziemlich viele: „Wearables“ warnen vor Herzinfarkt, H..."
  15: "Frank Griesel/Palmer Hargreaves"
  16: "Bild: Deutsche Telekom"
  17: "Partner:"
  18: "WeBridgeInnovation: Solve innovation challenges and win cash prizes, f..."
  19: "Sign up as an Entrepreneur, Scientist, Citizen Scientist, Administrato..."
  20: "Foto oben: Markus Wegner/www.pixelio.de"

```

Figure 54 - "Spielerisch Daten erheben" document stored in *projects_pro_list* collection. Example of description descriptors to remove.

This process is done in *STG_projects_pro_list* and after "cleaning" it, if this project has not been stored in *CSTrack_projects_descriptors* collection yet, the process inserts the whole document there (Figure 55). If it exists in the collection, then those descriptors that contain additional information are updated.

```

_id: ObjectId("5f4cb1b60f142d4cc42c6521")
TITLE: "Spielerisch Daten erheben"
DESCRIPTION: Array
  0: "Dahinter verbirgt sich ein mobiles App-Spiel, mit dem Wissenschaftler ..."
  1: "Sea Hero Quest ist jedoch nicht nur einfach ein weiteres App-Spiel von..."
  2: "Interview"
  3: "Herr Dr. Wehmeier, die Telekom unterstützt mit einem App-Spiel die Dem..."
  4: "Da gibt es schon ziemlich viele: „Wearables“ warnen vor Herzinfarkt, H..."
  5: "Frank Griesel/Palmer Hargreaves"
  6: "Bild: Deutsche Telekom"
Plat Id: "32"
Plat country: "DEU"
Insert date: "2020-08-31"
STATUS: Array
  Url platform: "http://www.citizen-science-germany.de/citizen_science_projekte..."
  Wp2 Id: 32
  Language: "German"

```

Figure 55 - "Spielerisch Daten erheben" document stored in *CSTrack_projects_descriptors* collection which contains the list of descriptors and information classified.

Example 4 - Topics descriptor (Scistarter and DabasDati platform)

In this example the process to classify topics information SciStarter platform, spanish citizen science and DabasDati platform is explained

The platforms where we extract the list of projects are <https://scistarter.org/> identified with the Id: 3 and <https://dabasdati.lv/en/cat/7/?links=en/cat/7/> identified with the Id: 39 as it can see in [wp2 list](#). We also identified other relevant information and stored it in this list, like the data status, which is placed in columns R, S, T and U and correspond to the steps explained before.

For the first platform (SciStarter), once the project's links are extracted as it is described in the previous sections, there is to extract the data. **First step** is to identify where the information is placed and what html tag is used. Scistarter uses the element “TOPICS” to inform topics and uses the tag “th” for the title and “td” for the information (Figure 56).

Figure 56 - “The Great Millipede Project” project from SciStarter platform. Topic information is in tag “tr”.

To perform the classification automatically, it is defined in *CSTrack_config* collection a list of possible values that can be displayed in different platforms to inform Topics (Figure 57).

Figure 57 - *CSTrack_config* collection where is defined a list of possible texts to inform Topics.

Second step is to automatically check if any of the values of the collection list is in the text extracted and then if it is, the texts are stored in the Topics descriptor.

For the second platform (DabasDati) all the information was extracted manually and Topics descriptor contains information on column “GRUPA” where groups of topics are described (Figure 58).

GRUPA	NOTEICĒJS	IZDEVĒJS	GADS
AUGI	Bioloģiski vērtīgo zaļāju augu indikatoru noteicējs	Latvijas Dabas fonds	2009
	Dzegužpirkstīšu <i>Dactylorhiza</i> noteicējs	Latvijas Dabas fonds	2012
	Dzegužpuķu <i>Orchis</i> noteicējs	Latvijas Dabas fonds	2012
	Grīšļu noteicējs	Latvijas Dabas fonds	2017
	Ezeru krastmalu augu noteicējs	Latvijas Dabas fonds	2016
	Papaīžu noteicējs	Latvijas Dabas fonds	2017
	Rasenu <i>Drosera</i> noteicējs	Latvijas Dabas fonds	2012
	Staipekņu noteicējs	Latvijas Dabas fonds	2012
	Vizbulu noteicējs	Latvijas Dabas fonds	2012

Figure 58 - *DabasDati* platform. Column “GRUPA” informs groups of topics.